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Automatic Trip End Imputation from Smartphone-based Travel Surveys

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INTRODUCTION

Travel behavior research and transportation demand modeling, which can be used to support transportation demand management policies, have received increasing attention recently due to ever-growing traffic congestions (Yao, Hu, Lu, Gao, & Zhang, 2014; Yu, Yang, & Yao, 2009). A travel survey is commonly used to collect travel information for travel demand analysis and modeling purposes. However, conventional travel surveys, which are generally conducted by paper-and-pencil interviews (PAPI), computer-assisted telephone interviews (CATI) and/or computer-assisted self-interviews (CASI), might impose a heavy burden on respondents since the detailed information of all the trips, including trip timing, travel modes and trip purposes, need to be recalled or recorded during the survey period. Fatigue becomes especially serious for multi-day travel surveys. Such fatigue in respondent might decrease the quality of collected data and pose an adverse effect on travel behavior research.

Furthermore, some travel details are usually reported approximately. Wolf et al. (Jean Wolf, Hallmark, Oliveira, Guensler, & Sarasua, 1999) reported that trip start and end time, as well as trip distance, tended to be rounded in self-reporting surveys. Another disadvantage of conventional surveys is that trip rate might be underestimated. Du and Aultman-Hall (2007) indicated that short trips or trip chains were easily omitted when respondents were required to complete the travel log at the end of the day or the entire survey period.

It is widely accepted that GPS-based data collection methods offer substantial advantages over traditional survey methods (Chen, Gong, Lawson, & Bialostozky, 2010; Dowds, Sullivan, & Aultman-Hall, 2013; Kim, Lee, Yang, & Do Yu, 2012; Leclerc, Trépanier, & Morency, 2013; Liu, Janssens, Wets, & Cools, 2013; Rieser-Schüssler, 2012). Chief among these advantages is the alleviation of respondent burden (Bricka, Zmud, Wolf, & Freedman, 2009; Jean Wolf et al., 1999; Zhou & Golledge, 2007).

With reduced efforts, respondents are more likely to report detailed travel information for a longer period. This in turn increases the quality of data and provides an opportunity to examine multi-day travel patterns (Hanson & Hildebrand, 2011; Shalaby & Roorda, 2011). The application of GPS technology, although sets a high demand to post-process data streams, improves data accuracy significantly. With the use of GPS units, trip rates are expected to be corrected due to an accurate location acquisition of the devices (Forrest & Pearson, 2005; P. Stopher, FitzGerald, & Xu, 2007).

In addition, the information about travel routes can also be collected in GPS travel surveys (Frignani, Auld, Mohammadian, Williams, & Nelson, 2010).

Dedicated GPS devices and smartphones are usually used to collect positioning data in GPS travel surveys. However, travel surveys based on the former are struggled with the following disadvantages: (1) a high cost for purchasing devices is undertaken; (2) incomplete data is usually collected since respondents tend to forget taking the devices with them; (3) devices need to be distributed and retrieved each time a respondent participates in this survey and (4) the sample size is restricted by the number of dedicated devices available.

Although respondent burdens are reduced and data accuracy is improved, the development of algorithms for inferring trip-related information is challenging (Shen & Stopher, 2014b). This study focuses on inference methods of trip ends (activity nodes) of individual-based travel surveys. This inference is considered to be the prerequisite to detect travel modes and trip purposes. Since distinct characteristics of trip ends are exhibited under the condition of GPS signal loss and normal recording, algorithms for detecting trip ends under these two scenarios are separately developed in most cases.

Under the scenario of GPS signal loss, it is well documented that the dwell time is a crucial parameter for inferring trip ends. Du and Aultman-Hall (2007) elaborated on proposed approaches used to infer trip ends from GPS track data streams collected by GPS units. The optimal values of the minimum dwell time and the maximum dwell time are set to be 40 and 140 seconds. In fact, the threshold of dwell time for detecting trip ends varies from 45 (Pearson, 2001) to 300 seconds (Doherty, Noël, Gosselin, Sirois, & Ueno, 2001; J Wolf, Schönfelder, Samaga, Oliveira, & Axhausen, 2004). The greatest threshold in available studies is 900 seconds (Schuessler & Axhausen, 2009), whereas the most frequently used one is 120 seconds.

Under the condition of GPS normal recording, the characteristics of trip ends are exhibited as 'point cloud' or rapid direction change. The former results from a stop lasting for a period of time, while the latter is caused by 'picking up or dropping off someone'. Therefore, trip ends with 'point cloud' can be detected by determining whether the number of continuous track points located within a certain distance around a point exceeds a given threshold. In other words, the density of observations is calculated to detect trip ends (Schuessler & Axhausen, 2009; P. R. Stopher, Jiang, & FitzGerald, 2005). Different threshold values are found in existing studies (Doherty et al., 2001; Schuessler & Axhausen, 2009; P. R. Stopher et al., 2005).

When the point density of a sequence of observations lasting for 10 minutes or including 300 points was higher than 15 for at least two-thirds of the points, trip ends were flagged by Schuessler and Axhausen (2009). This point density was calculated by counting the number of GPS points positioned in 30 preceding or 30 succeeding GPS points located

within a 15-meter radius around the point in question. In this rule, up to seven parameters were determined according to practical experience. Another case is rapid direction change due to 'picking up or dropping off someone'. P. R. Stopher et al. (2005) indicated that trip ends were identified when heading direction changed between 178 and 182 degrees during a duration of 30 seconds.

The effectiveness of proposed algorithms and the selection of calibrated parameters need to be assessed by comparing the inferred trip ends with the actual ones. To retrieve actual travel information, existing studies have asked respondents to take GPS devices and record travel logs, several of which were paper-based (Du & Aultman-Hall, 2007; Gong, Chen, Bialostozky, & Lawson, 2012) while others were web-based (Bohte & Maat, 2009; KOCHAN, BELLEMANS, JANSSENS, & WETS, 2006; Ohmori, Nakazato, & Harata, 2005).

Paper-based travel logs are not obtained by researchers until travel surveys are completed, while web-based logs, which were typically completed via personal digital assistants, smartphones or personal computers, are available immediately after they are submitted. Recently, prompted recall surveys have emerged as effective surveys to improve the accuracy of the travel information collected. In such surveys, respondents usually receive a map with travel trajectories of one day based on geographical information system (GIS) sources. This map can be used to prompt respondents to recall more detailed travel information. Some prompted recall surveys even display their travel information derived from raw positioning data streams (Greaves, Fifer, Ellison, & Germanos, 2010).

All the studies discussed above promote GPS-based surveys substantially. They, however, all leave room for improvement. Most researches employ specific values for parameters on the basis of their experience and neglect the possibility of achieving a better prediction accuracy by selecting an optimal parameter combination from a list of candidates. Distinct empirical values might be determined by different researchers even for the same dataset when trip ends are detected, indicating that the effectiveness of parameter values highly depend on empirical experience of researchers.

In terms of travel information acquisition, P. Stopher et al. (2007) concluded that self-administered surveys (by paper or by Internet) may encounter significant underreporting because there are no interviewers involved to prompt respondents to recall more detailed information. This paper, thus, focuses on developing algorithms for inferring trip ends and selecting the optimal parameter combination from pre-defined candidates by comparing derived trip ends with actual ones collected by interviewers-intervened travel surveys based on smartphones.

DATA COLLECTION

The data utilized to detect trip ends was collected in a smartphone-based travel survey launched at Shanghai city with three waves from mid-October 2013 to late-May 2014. A flowchart of the survey is shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** Some respondents are recruited by Internet, while others are invited by social networks of our group members. Once a respondent is recruited, he/she is required to install a positioning application developed by our research group and report their socio-demographic attributes and habitual destinations online. An exclusive user ID is automated from 1 in ascending order at an interval of 1 in the application to identify the respondent. Respondents are asked to start the application prior to leaving home for the first time and upload track data before close it after the last arrival home every day during the survey lasting at least five days.

Regarding the data transmission, respondents are recommended to upload the positioning data with Wi-Fi networks. Also, the cost for uploading track data is negligible even for cellular networks in the sense that the flow size is no greater than 20 kilobytes for positioning data of an entire day. After respondents upload GPS track data streams to the central server, travel information, including trip ends, travel modes and trip purposes, can be derived and displayed on a map, whereby respondents are interviewed by telephone to validate the derived travel information. The information will be corrected if necessary. The intervention of interviewers can prompt respondents to recall more details about their trips, which can help to collect actual travel information to a maximum degree and provide reliable data for evaluating proposed algorithms and selected parameters

Android and IOS are selected as platforms to develop the application due to high marketing penetration rates. As shown in Error! Reference source not found., the application records UTC time, latitude, longitude, altitude, the instantaneous speed, heading, the number of satellites in view and HDOP (Horizontal Dilution of Precision) once every second with GPS technology. While the positioning information of cellular triangulation is also collected, it is not used to infer trip ends in the current study due to its relatively low positioning accuracy. In addition, the time of uploading data for the last time is displayed to inform respondents about when the data has been uploaded.

We present each respondent with an external battery package valued at about 50 renminbi used to avoid battery drainage since GPS data is recorded in a relatively high frequency in this study. Also, the package is regarded as a motivation for respondents to participate in this survey. In fact, the application is

automatically closed when a stationary state are kept for more than five minutes and restarted when the smartphone move again. This function is designed to decrease battery consumption to a maximum extent, with no adverse effects on data recording for trips. Track data streams are originally stored in the corresponding smartphone when they are recorded.

Each time a user uploads track data, the uploaded data is deleted to conserve storage space on the device. As mentioned above, the size is no greater than 20 kilobytes for positioning data of an entire day. This data size is considered to be minor for smartphones that possess a capacity measured with Gigabytes. Therefore, the issue of memory usage can be nearly neglected in this survey. After the survey is completed, each respondent is presented with a mobile recharge card valued at 50 renminbi to attract more respondents to participate in the survey.

MainActivity	
您的用户编号是 : 139	⇒ user ID
当前位置(GPS)	⇒ current location (GPS)
当前位置(百度基站)	⇒ current location (cellular positioning)
上传轨迹(2013-12-22 12:23:02)	⇒ upload track data
退出	⇒ quit
GPS定位信息: 时间 : 2013-12-22 15:24:58 纬度 : 30.73172988 经度 : 121.34141813 速度 : 1.0米/秒 3.6公里/小时 海拔 : 30.200000762939453米 方向 : 230.1度 误差 : 43.0米' 卫星数量 : 5	⇒ positioning information of GPS
百度基站定位信息 : 时间 : 2013-12-22 15:24:23 网络类型 : 68 纬度 : 30.735486	⇒ positioning information of cellular positioning

GPS positioning data and travel information are taken as inputs for detecting trip ends. An example of GPS positioning data is shown in

Table 1. It can be seen from this table that signal loss exists in this example. Longitude, latitude and altitude indicate a position where the smartphone is located, while HDOP and the number of satellites in view represent the positioning accuracy. In this study, 885 person-day track data of 155 respondents are recorded.

Since the number of person-days with no trips reaches 127 and track data streams of 283 person-days are incomplete, only 2512 trip ends are obtained from this survey. On average, 3.9 trip ends are recorded for positioning data of a complete person-

day, while only 2.3 trip ends are retrieved for positioning data of an incomplete person-day. The maximum number of trip ends recorded for a person-day is 13.

These trip ends are all validated by respondents during prompted recall telephone surveys based on smartphones. Regarding locations of these trip ends, the number of trip ends that can match home, workplace, other habitual locations and non-habitual locations is 627, 503, 473 and 909, respectively. In total, 2153063 track points are recorded and uploaded to the central server. On average, 3368 track points are recorded for complete positioning data of one person-day, while 1955 track points are retrieved for incomplete positioning data of one person-day.

Table 1 Example of GPS Positioning Data

User Id	UTC Time	Longitude	Latitude	Altitude	Speed (KPH)	Heading	HDOP	# of satellites
436	2014/5/22 13:11:59	121.2000074	31.01405345	55.3	0	208.4	1.4	6
436	2014/5/22 13:12:00	121.200022	31.01408392	55.7	0.3	208.4	1.4	6
436	2014/5/22 13:12:01	121.2000355	31.01410736	54.9	0.7	28.5	1.4	6
436	2014/5/22 13:12:02	121.2000439	31.0141283	54.8	1	25.4	1.4	6
436	2014/5/22 13:12:03	121.200048	31.01415285	55.4	0.9	20.2	1.3	6
436	2014/5/22 13:12:04	121.2000532	31.01417158	55.1	0.7	15.9	1.4	6
436	2014/5/22 13:12:10	121.2000151	31.0141569	56.6	1	219.3	1.6	5
436	2014/5/22 13:12:11	121.2000078	31.01414432	56.4	1.1	218.4	1.6	6
436	2014/5/22 13:12:12	121.1999997	31.01413599	56.6	1.1	215.3	1.6	6
436	2014/5/22 13:12:13	121.1999936	31.01412758	56.7	1.3	207.4	1.5	6
436	2014/5/22 13:12:15	121.1999776	31.01412614	57.5	1.2	210.2	1.4	5
436	2014/5/22 13:12:16	121.1999683	31.01413566	58	1	215.7	1.4	5
436	2014/5/22 13:12:17	121.1999648	31.01415118	59	0.8	224.5	1.3	4
436	2014/5/22 13:12:20	121.1999765	31.01415226	59.2	0.3	224.5	1.3	6
436	2014/5/22 13:12:21	121.1999938	31.01414781	58.9	0.4	224.5	1.2	6
436	2014/5/22 13:12:22	121.2000089	31.014147	58.9	0.5	224.5	1.2	6
436	2014/5/22 13:12:24	121.2000261	31.01414929	58.8	0.5	224.5	1.2	6

INFERRING TRIP ENDS

Inferring trip ends is the most crucial issue to be handled in this study. The inference process includes three primary procedures: GPS data cleaning and pre-processing, trip end inference from GPS data streams and trip end rearrangement. Two cases including signal loss and ongoing track recording need to be investigated when trip ends are detected. GPS signal loss usually arises when respondents are located in an indoor environment or neighbourhood affected by 'city canyon'. A dwell lasting for a certain period of time for trip ends with signal loss is exhibited, while 'point clustering' or a rapid change of heading is presented for trip ends with GPS normal recording.

GPS Data Cleaning and Pre-processing

The GPS data streams must be cleaned and pre-processed before they can be used to infer travel information. The raw data streams are cleaned with

the following three steps so that incomplete and inaccurate track points are removed. First, incomplete track points are deleted since they might indicate faulty records. Second, track points with less than four satellites in view or with an HDOP of more than 3 are also deleted to maintain a sufficient accuracy for detecting trip ends. The number of satellites in view indicates positioning accuracy, while HDOP determines how these satellites are dispersed. Third, track points with an altitude of more than 200 meters are eliminated since a maximum altitude of Shanghai city is not more than 200 meters and the average altitude is less than 50 meters. 206513 track points are removed from the dataset after the data is cleaned, i.e., about 9.59% of the track points are eliminated. This percentage is considered to be sufficiently minor relative to the frequency of once every second for recording data so that subsequent trip end inference can be effectively implemented with the remaining track points. There are also three steps to implement data pre-processing

to allow cleaned track data for ready use in the subsequent process of inferring trip ends. First, UTC time is converted to local date and time in Shanghai. Second, track data is extracted for each person-day according to user ID and the local date. Third, all track points of one person-day are re-numbered to facilitate trip end inference.

Trip End Inference with Signal Loss

The dwell time is utilized to determine whether there exist trip ends with signal loss. Intuitively, it usually requires a shorter dwell time to identify a trip end for the location matching habitual destinations than that for other places. Home and workplaces are the most frequent destinations, while other habitual destinations, such as the commonly visited grocery and gymnasium, may be visited once, twice a week and even every day. In contrast, non-habitual destinations, such as hospitals, are visited with a much less probability for the healthy. In addition,

habitual destinations take a percentage of as high as 63.81% in this study. While it seems to be more reasonable to employ different parameter values depending on the type of habitual destinations, the treatment cannot be supported by the relatively small sample size in this study. Thus, we define two different parameters for dwell time (t_1 and t_2) to determine whether there exists a trip end for a stop near habitual destinations or other places. To be specific, in the context of signal loss, a stop matching one of his/her habitual destinations with a dwell time of more than t_1 is flagged as a trip end, while a stop that does not match habitual destinations, requires a dwell time of more than t_2 to be flagged as a trip end. The last track point before the signal loss is generally considered as the starting point of the trip end, while the first point immediately after signal loss is considered to be the terminal point of the trip end. The values of the two parameters indicate the minimum period of time an activity requires.

Trip End Inference with Normal Recording

There exist two types of trip ends during normal recording: one is a trip end caused by ‘picking up and dropping off someone’, while the other is a trip end for other reasons. An abrupt change in direction is

usually presented for the former, while point clustering is always exhibited for the latter.

For trip ends caused by ‘picking up and dropping off someone’, the dwell time is inclined to be very short. Thus, another measure should be utilized instead of the critical dwell time. Although the change in

direction is usually used to detect trip ends for picking up or dropping off someone, it might falsely identify U-turn cases as trip ends. U-turn cases usually occur when one needs to reach a certain place on the other side of the road physically separated.

Generally, it is probable for the driver to choose an intersection nearest to his/her destination to complete the U-turn operation so that the length of links overlapped is minimized. In contrast, one usually chooses the same links to undertake trips before and

after picking up/dropping off someone (as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**). Thus, we extract the length of links overlapped before and after an abrupt heading change as a measure to determine whether there exists a trip end. If the length of overlapped links exceeds a critical length (μ), a trip end is flagged. On the contrary, if the length of overlapped links is too short to reach the critical length, it is assumed that there does not exist a trip end.

Another type of trip ends is typically detected using a clustering algorithm since track points are positioned closely to each other. This algorithm constructs a subset consisting of continuous GPS points during a specific period of time sequentially and then calculate the maximum distance between any two points in the subset. If the maximum distance does not exceed a critical distance (d), a trip end is flagged, and vice versa. For this algorithm, the period of time also indicates the minimum duration required by an activity so that it is assigned with the same value as the dwell time for detecting trip ends with signal loss.

The critical distance is another important parameter to determine whether there exists a trip end with normal recording. It is also one of the parameters to be determined in our study. If d is large, too many false trip ends may be detected for reasons like traffic congestions. However, if d is small, actual trip ends might be substantially neglected. Therefore, a reasonable critical distance is responsible for a high accuracy for trip end inference in the case of point cloud. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows an example of point clustering. For this example, the time difference reaches 13 minutes and track points are located in a highly minor field between trip 1 end and trip 2 start.

Trip End Rearrangement

After trip ends are detected, reconstruction and combination are performed since some trip ends might be detected twice or a single trip end may be identified as multiple ones. For example, one takes a trip to pick up a friend and waits for the friend for a sufficiently long time so that the trip end is simultaneously detected by both clustering rule and overlapped length rule. Also, a trip end might be split into several portions when one takes several stops in a park or a large-scale children's playground. Thus, we adopt two rules to rearrange trip ends identified by aforementioned three rules. First, two trip ends joined together or overlapped in terms of duration are combined to form a single one. Second, two neighbouring trip ends with straight distance less than 400 meters are merged according to the definition of a trip.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two types of errors are required to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed methods and the selection of parameters and to determine an optimal parameter combination. Error type 1 occurs when a trip end is inferred but does not actually exist, while error type 2 arises when an actual trip end is not detected successfully. Generally, error type 1 occurs when either signal loss occurs or traffic congestions exist, while error type 2 arises when short trips are undertaken or the parameters are unreasonably chosen. On one hand, if the parameters are set to detect trip ends easily, excessive identification tends to occur. An extreme example can be observed when all GPS points are detected as trip ends. For this case, error type 2 is zero; however, error type 1 is unacceptable. On the other hand, if the parameters are chosen to make it difficult to detect trip ends, trip ends tend to be omitted. An extreme example can be observed when no trip ends are detected. In this case, error type 1 is zero and error type 2 is intolerable. Therefore, a balance of these two error types is

required. In addition, given different cases, the order of severity of the two error types may differ. Therefore, the balance point may be determined with the purpose of inferring trip ends.

Two measures are used to assess the selection of parameters. The first measure, 'Error %' (the error rate), is based on error type 1 and defined by equation (1):

$$Error\% = \frac{N_{error}}{N_{real}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

(1)

where N_{error} denotes the number of trip ends that are inferred by the algorithm but do not actually exist, while N_{real} is the number of trip ends actually generated by respondents. This measure indicates the inclination of a specific parameter combination to falsely detect trip ends. Another measure, 'Complete %' (the detection rate), is based on error type 2 and defined by equation (2):

$$Complete\% = \frac{N_{correct}}{N_{real}} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

where $N_{correct}$ is the number of actual trip ends detected by the algorithm. This measure is utilized to evaluate the capacity of a specific parameter combination for detecting actual trip ends.

To optimize the parameter values in the inference algorithm, four parameters are tested: (1) the critical dwell time for detecting trip ends when habitual destinations are matched (t_1); (2) the critical dwell time for detecting trip ends when GPS location are located far away from habitual destinations (t_2); (3) the critical value for the maximum distance between any two points in a subset for detecting trip ends with ongoing recording (d); (4) the critical overlapped length of links before and after an abrupt direction change for detecting trip ends with ongoing recording (μ).

Since interaction of four parameters exists in terms of trip end inference, we test a list of parameter combinations instead of a single parameter one by one. Five different values for each parameter are tested. Due to the fact that 120 seconds is used as a critical dwell time in most existing literature, 60, 90, 120, 150 and 180 seconds are chosen to form a choice set for t_1 and t_2 . The reason to employ the same choice set for t_1 and t_2 is that we want to determine whether t_1 is less than t_2 for the optimal result. The choice set of d includes 5, 10, 15, 20 and 25 meters, while that of μ contains 0, 20, 40, 60 and 80 meters. The reason why 0 meters is included in the choice set is that we want to see whether setting a critical overlapped length is better than not (i.e., 0 meters). Thus, a total of 625 different parameter combinations are tested. The preferable results are shown in Table 4.

The results in TABLE 2 indicate, as one has expected, that the cost of decreasing false detection of additional trip ends is a lower detection rate of actual trip ends as a whole. This means that a parameter combination incorporating a high capability of capturing actual trip ends intends to present a high inclination to detect false trip ends. For

different parameter combinations, the results differ significantly, which demonstrates that the result is highly sensitive to parameter selection. The preferable parameter combinations are listed in the table.

The fact that t_1 is always less than or equal to t_2 in the table implies that the critical dwell time utilized to detect trip ends when habitual destinations is matched should not be longer than that for other places. This difference of t_1 and t_2 also demonstrates the necessity of employing two distinct values for critical dwell time. For the critical distance, the fact that five different values all appear in the table seems to imply a diversity of characteristics when point clustering arises. Specifically, during a trip end, some might nearly hold still, while others might walk up and down within a small area. Alternatively, these different characteristics might be caused by different accuracy of GPS positioning in a different environment. For the critical overlapped length, it proves the necessity of adopting this measure in detecting trip ends that 0 meters does not appear in the table. In other words, the inclusion of the critical overlapped length effectively distinguish trips for picking up/dropping off some from U-turn cases.

TABLE 2 Trip Ends Identification Results

Serial Number	Parameters				Results			
	Dwell Time (t_1)	Dwell Time (t_2)	Critical Distance (d)	Critical Overlapped Length (μ)	No. of Trip Ends Correctly Detected	Complete % (detection rate)	No. of Trip Ends Falsely Detected	Error % (error rate)
1	60	60	5	60	2118	84.32	131	5.21
2	60	60	10	40	2135	84.99	140	5.57
3	30	90	10	80	2289	91.12	96	3.82
4	60	90	15	60	2282	90.84	113	4.50
5	90	120	5	60	2278	90.68	99	3.94
6	90	120	10	40	2243	89.29	86	3.42
7	60	120	10	60	2274	90.53	89	3.54
8	90	120	15	80	2305	91.76	113	4.50
9	120	150	5	80	2332	92.83	111	4.42
10	120	150	10	20	2310	91.96	101	4.02
11	90	150	10	40	2354	93.71	89	3.54
12	90	150	10	60	2412	96.02	119	4.74
13	90	150	10	80	2381	94.79	109	4.34
14	120	150	15	80	2331	92.79	96	3.82
15	60	150	25	60	2356	93.79	99	3.94
16	90	150	20	60	2281	90.80	87	3.46
17	60	180	10	40	2341	93.19	102	4.06
18	90	180	10	80	2318	92.28	94	3.74
19	90	180	15	40	2235	88.97	91	3.62
20	120	180	20	60	2198	87.50	88	3.50

An optimal parameter combination needs to be determined according to the accuracy of both detection rate and error rate. On the whole, there does not exist a combination that achieves the highest detection rate and the lowest error rate simultaneously. However, a high detection rate is

regarded as more preferable because the error rate can be further decreased by introducing such rules as intersection matching to eliminate false trip ends. Consequently, parameter combination 12 is selected. The combination achieves a detection rate of as high as 96.02% with a low error rate of 4.74%. For this

parameter combination, the values of t_1 , t_2 , d and μ are 90 seconds, 150 seconds, 10 meters and 60 meters, respectively. The big difference between t_1 and t_2 in the optimal parameter combination demonstrates the necessity of employing different parameters for inferring trip ends when habitual destinations are matched or not. It is thus clear that collecting habitual destinations before the survey starts provides a favourable opportunity to improve distinction for algorithms inferring trip ends, although it might pose an extra burden on respondents. The critical dwell time of 150 seconds is higher than 120 seconds adopted by most existing studies (Shen & Stopher, 2014a). The discrepancy might be caused by a relatively congested transportation network in such a megacity as Shanghai city, where dwell time needs to last for as long as 150 seconds to detect a trip end for non-habitual destinations. The critical distance for the clustering algorithm is set as the same value as a study by Bohte W., and K. Maat (Bohte & Maat, 2009). The might indicate that the GPS positioning has little difference in terms of location accuracy in different cities. 60 meters are taken as the optimal critical length for overlapped links instead of 0 meters, which demonstrates that employing this parameter is preferable when we try to detect trip ends caused by picking up/dropping off someone.

Under the condition of the optimal combination, the number of trip ends that are not detected reaches 6 (0.96%), 10 (1.99%), 21 (4.44%), 63 (6.93%) for home, workplaces, other habitual locations and non-habitual locations, respectively. Therefore, trips ends matched with habitual destinations are not detected with a much lower percentage (2.31%) than that for non-habitual locations (6.93%). This result demonstrates that parameters should be separately set for detecting trip ends for habitual locations and non-habitual locations.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This paper reported a travel survey based on smartphones in Shanghai. GPS positioning data streams were recorded passively, while travel information was confirmed by respondents using prompted recall surveys. A method optimizing parameter combinations was proposed in this paper. Parameter values obtained by this method is superior to specific values adopted by most existing studies since they provide an opportunity to substantially improve the accuracy of trip end inference and present a high robustness due to a less requirement of practical experience from researchers. In addition, three rules were applied to infer trip ends from GPS track data streams with achieving an optimal parameter combination according to two measures utilized to compare inferred trip ends and actual trip ends.

A promising detection rate of 96.02% and a low error rate of 4.74% was achieved. This performance indicates that smartphone-based travel surveys could

potentially supplement and even substitute for conventional travel survey in the future. It should be noted that all the GPS data streams are batch-processed by a program coded in Matlab. Thus, a smartphone-based travel survey may become a favourable model for launching large-scale GPS travel surveys. Low respondent burden and high accuracy of data merit this type of survey. In addition, this type of survey can be conducted more easily as the popularity of smartphones increases.

To reduce the survey cost and decrease respondent burdens, the travel information confirmation is expected not to be required when the accuracy of travel information detected is sufficiently improved so that it is much better than that of data collected in traditional travel surveys. Additionally, it can be anticipated that an optimal parameter for a different city might be different from that employed in our study. However, this study is still illuminated since researchers can utilize the method proposed in this study to achieve an optimal parameter combination suitable for their targeted city environment. In addition, the cost of each respondent in this survey is about 100 renminbi. Since each respondent participates in a survey of at least five days, the average cost of a person-day ranges from 15 to 20 renminbi. This cost is significantly lower than that of most GPS surveys conducted (Stecher, Chesebro, & Zhang, 2014).

According to travel information validated by prompted recall telephone surveys, falsely inferred trip ends are primarily caused by: (1) long-term traffic congestions, especially near intersections or (2) signal loss due to cold start or city canyon or (3) delayed start of the positioning software during some trips, while actual trip ends that are not inferred typically occur during GPS signal loss. To further decrease the number of falsely inferred trip ends and actual trip ends that are not inferred, we could make efforts in the following aspects in the further research: (1) identify whether a potential trip end is located at an intersection with a GIS source and extract features shared by trip ends falsely detected; (2) make up for incomplete trip chains by utilizing multiple types of positioning data, such as cellular data; (3) decide whether data streams uploaded by respondents are complete automatically and remind respondents to maintain complete GPS records as much as possible; (4) distinguish congested areas from general transportation analysis zones (such as urban and suburb areas) and employ different critical dwell time to enhance the performance of the algorithms. However, the first and the last aspects require an acquisition of a GIS source, which is hardly available for us. As a result, it is highly meaningful to develop an inference algorithm without a GIS source, as stated in this study. In addition, it is helpful to remind respondents to start the positioning application in time to keep a relatively complete track data for inferring trip ends, which could improve the detection accuracy to some extent.

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